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Inoyatov Amrillo Shodiyevich
Saidova Mukhlisa Akhrorovna
Tashkent State Dental Institute
Mukhlisa_saidova95@mail.ru

MICROCIRCULATORY DISTURBANCES IN PATIENTS WITH POST-COVID SYNDROME AND TROPHIC ULCERS OF THE MUCOSUS MEMBRANE OF THE ORAL CAVITY

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ABSTRACT

The Covid 19 pandemic, which has affected more than 400 million people worldwide, about 20-30% of patients, does not fully recover and continues to experience post-COVID syndrome (PCS). One of these symptoms is the appearance of trophic ulcers on the oral mucosa (OM). One of the likely mechanisms for the development of trophic ulcers in the oral cavity is a violation of the microcirculation of blood and lymphatic vessels. An important non-invasive method for diagnosing the state of capillary blood flow in trophic ulcers of the oral mucosa in patients with a history of Covid 19 is the determination of the microcirculation of tissue vessels.

Keywords: COVID-19, trophic ulcer, microcirculation, capillary blood flow, laser Doppler flowmetry.

Иноятлов Амрилло Шодиевья
Саидова Мухлиса Ахроровна

Ташкентский государственный стоматологический институт
Mukhlisa_saidova95@mail.ru

МИКРОЦИРКУЛЯТОРНЫЕ НАРУШЕНИЯ ПАЦИЕНТОВ С ПОСТКОВИДНЫМ СИНДРОМОМ И ТРОФИЧЕСКИМИ ЯЗВАМИ СЛИЗИСТОЙ ОБОЛОЧКИ ПОЛОСТИ РТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Пандемия Covid 19, поразила более 400 миллионов людей в мире, около 20-30 % пациентов, полностью не выздоравливают и продолжают испытывать постковидный синдром (ПКС). Одним из таких симптомов является появление трофических язв на слизистой оболочке полости рта (СОПР). Одним из вероятных механизмов развития трофических язв в полости рта является нарушение микроциркуляции кровеносных и лимфатических сосудов. Важным неинвазивным методом для диагностики состояния капиллярного кровотока при трофических язвах СОПР у больных, имевших в анамнезе Covid 19, является определение микроциркуляции сосудов тканей.

Ключевые слова: COVID-19, трофическая язва, микроциркуляция, капиллярный кровоток, лазерная доплеровская флоуметрия.

Inoyatov Amrillo Shodiyevich
Saidova Muxlisa Axrorovna
Toshkent Davlat Stomatologiya Instituti
Mukhlisa_saidova95@mail.ru

POST-COVID SINDROMI VA OG'IZ BO'SHLIG'I SHILLIQ QAVATI TROFIK YARASI BOR BEMORLARDA MIKROSIRKULYATOR BUZISHLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Dunyo bo'ylab 400 milliondan ortiq odamni Covid 19 pandemiyasi zararlagan bo'lib, bemorlarning taxminan 20-30 foizini to'liq tuzalmaydi va post-COVID sindromini (PCS) boshdan kechirishda davom etmoqda. Ushbu alomatlardan biri og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavatida (OBShQ) trofik yaralarning paydo bo'lishidir. Og'iz bo'shlig'ida trofik yaralar rivojlanishining ehtimoliy mexanizmlaridan biri qon va limfa tomirlarining mikrosirkulyatsiyasi buzilishidir. Covid-19 boshdan kechirgan bemorlarda og'iz bo'shlig'i shilliq qavati trofik yaralarida kapillyar qon oqimining holatini diagnostika qilishning muhim noinvaziv usuli bu to'qima tomirlarining mikrosirkulyatsiyasini aniqlashdir.

Kalit so'zlar: COVID-19, trofik yara, mikrosirkulyatsiya, kapillyar qon oqimi, lazerli Doppler flovmetriya.

Relevance. Currently, the COVID-19 infection caused by coronavirus SARS-CoV-2, poses the greatest danger to life and health of mankind. This infection is accompanied systemic inflammation, often becoming chronic, and causes severe complications. The Covid 19 pandemic, which has affected more than 400 million people in the world, about 20-30% of patients have experienced the acute phase of COVID-19, do not fully recover and continue to experience post-COVID syndrome (PCS) lasting up to one year. One of these symptoms is a decrease in the efficiency of patients, increased fatigue, the appearance of trophic ulcers on the oral mucosa (OM), a decrease in appetite, which naturally affects the quality of life of patients. One of the likely mechanisms for the development of trophic ulcers in the oral cavity is the defeat of the endothelium of the capillary bed, which leads to a violation of the microcirculation of blood and lymphatic vessels [3,4,8,10]. In clinical studies of patients with COVID-19, microcirculatory changes were detected much earlier than changes in systemic hemodynamic parameters occurred [1,5,11,12,13,14]. An important non-invasive method for diagnosing the state of capillary blood flow in trophic ulcers of the oral mucosa in patients with a history of Covid 19 is the determination of the microcirculation of tissue vessels. [2,6,7,9].

The aim of the study is to study microcirculation in patients with PCS and trophic ulcers of the oral mucosa.

Materials and methods. The study involved patients of both sexes with a history of COVID-19 and the appearance of a trophic ulcer on the oral mucosa. For control, the study included people without severe background pathology of the same age who were not infected with the virus. 125 people were examined, of which 104 were patients with trophic oral ulcers after COVID-19 and 21 were healthy individuals who were included in the control group. The study included people aged 18-70 years, including 61 men and 43 women. The average age of the examined patients was 56.7±0.9 years.

The study included 104 patients with a trophic ulcer on the ORM with a confirmed diagnosis of COVID-19 (according to PCR and CT of the lungs), complicated by pneumonia and signed consent to the study. Patients with a diagnosis of urinary tract infections, diseases of the endocrine and cardiovascular systems, neuropsychiatric disorders, malignant tumors, pregnant and lactating women were excluded from the study.

To study the state of microcirculation in the vessels of the OMPR by the method of laser Doppler flowmetry (LDF), a laser capillary blood flow analyzer LAKK-02, manufactured by NPP Lazma LLC (Russia), was used. The LDF-gram was processed using the software: the average value

of tissue perfusion with blood was calculated - M, "flux" - the standard deviation of basal blood flow fluctuations - RMS, the coefficient of variation of blood flow - Kv, IEM - microcirculation efficiency index, integral indicator of the ratio of active and passive blood flow modulation mechanisms (conventional units).

An analysis of the amplitude-frequency spectrum of Dopplerograms was carried out, among them very low-frequency oscillations associated with periodic contractions of endotheliocytes - $A\alpha/M \cdot 100\%$ were taken into account; low frequency associated with the activity of smooth myocytes in arterioles $ALF/M \cdot 100\%$; pulse fluctuations caused by changes in intravascular pressure synchronized with the heart rate - $ACF/M \cdot 100\%$, as well as fluctuations associated with peripheral changes in the venous vascular bed, associated with respiratory excursions - $ANF/M \cdot 100\%$.

Statistical analysis of the materials was carried out using the IBM SPSS Statistics v.23 software package (developer - IBM Corporation), Pearson's χ^2 test was used. Significance of differences was considered established at $p < 0.05$.

Results. A functional examination of patients with trophic ulcers for oral mucosa using laser Doppler fluometry showed that all parameters were obtained using the software of the laser analyzer of capillary blood flow "LAKK-02" and characterized the blood flow microcirculation.

When the sensor is installed in the area of the studied microvasculature, the received sound signal is characterized as a quiet monotonous, not synchronized with the phases of the cardiac cycle. The visual signal resembles a monophasic curve. When comparing the average statistical parameters of blood flow velocity in the studied segments in patients aged 21–35 years who underwent COVID-19, it was found that the indicators of linear and volumetric blood flow velocity in patients of both groups were in the same range of values and there were statistically significant decreases in microcirculation parameters compared to the group control. There was a decrease in the total perfusion of capillaries with blood, which was recorded by a decrease in the integral index of microcirculation - M in patients of the comparison group with PKC by 20.09% ($P < 0.01$); in patients after suffering COVID-19 and trophic ulcers - the main group - by 36.65% ($P < 0.05$); the corresponding dynamics of erythrocyte flow fluctuation (σ) was 13.22% ($P < 0.05$) and 20.0% ($P < 0.05$); coefficient of variation Kv in % - by 11.1% ($P < 0.05$) and 19.05% ($P < 0.05$); fluxmotion efficiency index, reflecting the ratio of active and passive mechanisms of microcirculation - by 14.8% ($P < 0.05$) and 22.74% ($P < 0.05$); the intensity of fluctuations due to the concentration of endotheliocytes in the vessel wall - by 17.20% ($P < 0.05$) and 32.97% ($P < 0.01$), blood flow fluctuations due to the contraction of myocytes in the microvessel wall ($ALF / M \cdot 100\%$) - by 13.50% ($P < 0.05$) and 31.25% ($P < 0.05$); decrease in the contribution of heart contractions to microcirculatory hemodynamics ($ACF/M \cdot 100\%$) - by 18.91% ($P < 0.05$) and 31.15% ($P < 0.05$) and a decrease in the contribution of the respiratory component ($AHF/M \cdot 100\%$) - by 12.75% ($P < 0.05$) and 21.15% ($P < 0.05$).

Table 1
Microcirculation Indicators In Healthy Persons And Patients With Post-Covid Syndrome (Pcs)

Indicators		Control group n=21	Comparison group n=52	Main group, n=52
1	M, perf.unit.	17,32±0,72	13,82±0,66°	11,31±0,51 ^{o^}
2	σ , perf.unit.	2,85±0,11	2,56±0,11°	2,37±0,09 ^{o^}
3	Kv	17,11±0,82	15,21±0,71°	13,85±0,63 ^{o^}
4	IEM	1,62±0,05	1,38±0,05°	1,15±0,03 ^{o^}
5	$A\alpha/M \cdot 100\%$	10,82±0,45	9,03±0,40°	7,22±0,31 ^{o^}
6	$ALF/ M \cdot 100\%$	9,02±0,36	7,70±0,38°	6,20±0,28 ^{o^}
7	$ACF/ M \cdot 100\%$	15,45±0,63	12,53±0,62°	10,53±0,50 ^{o^}
8	$AHF/ M \cdot 100\%$	9,42±0,44	8,21±0,37°	6,32±0,37 ^{o^}

Note: ° - $P < 0.05$ compared to control;

^ - $P < 0.05$ compared with the comparison group.

From the data in Table 1 it can be seen that for all studied microcirculatory parameters, more pronounced changes were recorded in the group of patients with post-covid syndrome and trophic ulcers, the difference between them was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

The microcirculation disturbances noted by us in patients with post-covid syndrome associated with trophic ulcers can be one of the most important dominant pathogenetic links characterizing the severity of the disease in this category of patients.

Fig.1 Dynamics of microcirculation parameters in patients with post-covid syndrome (PCS) and trophic ulcers in relation to the indicators of the control group.

Obviously, a significant contribution to the violation of microcirculation in patients who have undergone COVID-19 with trophic ulcers of the OM is made by previously established biologically active substances involved in the activation of damage to vascular endothelial cells, as well as pathomorphological changes in tissues with sclerotic lesions of blood vessels and nerve fibers.

Conclusion. Thus, according to the conducted functional studies to determine tissue microcirculation in patients with post-covid syndrome and trophic ulcers of the oral mucosa, the pathogenetic mechanism of these disorders, obviously, is endothelial dysfunction of damage by inflammatory mediators of the vascular endothelium, especially in patients after covid pneumonia, which leads to damage to the microvasculature and deterioration of cellular metabolism.

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